

Performance study of hybrid upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor treating slaughterhouse wastewater

Loganath R.* and Debabrata Mazumder

Civil Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur, Howrah-711 103, West Bengal, India

E-mail : loganath.rk@gmail.com, debabrata@civil.iiests.ac.in

Manuscript received 15 December 2017, accepted 26 February 2018

Abstract : Anaerobic wastewater treatment process has quickly risen as a viable option for treating high-strength wastewater. A large amount of slaughterhouse wastewater is generated during meat product manufacturing due to the cleaning process. It contains high concentrations of organic matter, oil and grease, and nitrogenous compounds (proteins and amino acids). Hence, its treatment before discharge is necessary for protection of the water environment. Given the high biodegradability of slaughterhouse wastewater, biological processes are considered to be suitable for organic matter removal. The performance of a laboratory-scale Hybrid Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket Reactor (HUASBR) has been studied in semi batch mode of operation for the removal of organic carbon from Slaughter House Wastewater (SHWW). The reactor was operated under initial Mixed Liquor Suspended Solids (MLSS) concentration 25000–30000 mg/L. Total batch period was taken maximum 72 h and the influent chemical oxygen demand (COD) was provided in the range of 1000 ± 50 mg/L to 4200 ± 50 mg/L. It was observed that 74% of COD removal could be obtained at the end of 72 h. Apart from that a steady gas production was noticed.

Keywords : Anaerobic digestion, HUASB reactor, slaughterhouse wastewater, COD removal, biogas generation.

I. Introduction

High strength wastewater is categorized by the concentration of the organic matter, solids, oil and greases. It is essentially generated from the manufacturing process involving a considerable loss of organic raw materials during production^{1–6}. High strength wastewater is a matter of concern due to presence of objectionable colour, pH, high COD, BOD, significant amount of nitrogen matter along with enough suspended solids in some cases. It is also potentially harmful by virtue of high oxygen demanding potential leading to rapid DO depletion in the water body upon discharge^{7–10}. Slaughterhouse wastewater holds high amount of suspended and colloidal components in the form of fats, proteins and cellulose, which have adverse effects on the environment^{11–15}. This wastewater can be treated by means of anaerobic digestion as it has high concentrations of biodegradable organic contents, sufficient

alkalinity, and adequate amount of nitrogen and phosphorus^{16–21}. Effluent from abattoir is moderate to high strength complex wastewater containing about 45% soluble and 55% coarse suspended organics. Most of the organics emanate from blood and offal. The composition and flow generally depend on the number of animals killed. Discharge of slaughterhouse wastewater without treatment can lead to degradation of the aquatic environment and pollution in the irrigation water^{22,23}. Fixed media support plays an important role to accommodate more and more attached biomass which enhances the rate of COD removal and separation of the gas from the biomass^{24,25}.

II. Materials and methods

A. Design and fabrication of reactor setup

The reactor was designed following the principle of anaerobic hybrid bioreactor. It is a combination

of the anaerobic sludge blanket and the anaerobic filter, where wastewater was allowed to flow in upward direction. Depending on the Organic Loading Rate (OLR), the volume/density of the sludge blanket can be adjusted. Similarly, the amount of attached surface in the media, rather the number of media can also be adjusted for treating the organic matter, left out from the anaerobic sludge blanket.

The filter media is nothing but the unit material, on which biofilm is allowed to grow up. This additional biomass, attached onto the media enhances the treatment efficiency of the Hybrid Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (HUASB) reactor, used in the study. In earlier days, rock, brick bats, earthen rings were used for the attached growth purpose. At present, various polymeric materials are being used and among them polypropylene was found to be cost-effective. Therefore, in the present study the filter media, made of polypropylene was used for good attachment of microorganism.

A laboratory scale Hybrid Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (HUASB) reactor of 13.51 liters capacity was fabricated for performance evaluation. It was fabricated using transparent acrylic fiber with diameter of 15 cm, height of 60 cm and wall thickness of 5 mm. Nine sampling ports were provided along its height at equal distance. Inlet was made towards the bottom of the reactor, so the feed stroke at the bottom. An outlet was provided at the top of the filter media, which was connected to the effluent tank. On the top of the reactor a gas solid separator was provided to separate gas and solid raised due to the upward movement of the feed. The gas outlet was connected through rubber tubing to the liquid displacement system to measure the gas production. The amount of gas produced is equal to the amount of liquid displaced and hence gas produced can be measured at regular intervals of time. A filter media of height 15 cm made of polypropylene reticulated rings was provided at the top of the reactor. About 50 rings were packed in the reactor for consistency. The surface area of each ring was 7.1 cm^{-1} and the total surface area occupied by the packing was 355

cm^{-1} . The reactors were operated at mesophilic temperature ($37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). The schematic representation of HUASB reactor shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The schematic diagram of experimental setup of HUASB reactor.

B. Characterization of seed sludge

Anaerobic Digested Sludge was collected from the biogas plant located at Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narandrapur, Kolkata. The plant is a conventional single stage anaerobic digestion plant, which produces methane from cow dung slurry. Anaerobic Digested Sludge was taken from the bottom the sludge outlet tank. The characteristic of Anaerobic Digested Sludge is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of Anaerobic Digested Sludge

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value ^a	Std. deviation
1.	pH	6.9	0.95
2.	Alkalinity	555	32.71
3.	Total COD	2200	215.66
5.	Total Solids	36116	465.87
6.	Total Dissolved Solids	3028	894.51
7.	Total Suspended Solids	33087	1128.88
8.	Total Fixed Solids	10014	340.95
9.	Total Volatile Solids	26102	130.85
10.	BOD	1540	58.40

Note : All the values in mg/L except pH, alkalinity (CaCO_3).

^aAverage of three samples.

C. Characterization of wastewater

The study was carried out using slaughterhouse wastewater collected from an abattoir located at Tangra, Kolkata. The collected wastewater was stored in a freezer at a low temperature of about 4°C. The characteristic of an abattoir slaughterhouse wastewater is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of slaughterhouse wastewater

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value ^a	Std. deviation
1.	pH	7.4	0.105
2.	Alkalinity	242	38.57
3.	Total COD	8426	369.50
4.	Soluble COD	6294	184.75
5.	Total Solids	16262	345.13
6.	Total Dissolved Solids	8980	688.77
7.	Total Suspended Solids	7281	980.04
8.	Total Fixed Solids	2767	233.51
9.	Total Volatile Solids	13495	114.23
10.	BOD	5730	91.22
11.	Nitrogen	72	5.29
12.	TKN	426	8.00
13.	Phosphate	25	1.02

Note : All the values in mg/L except pH, salinity (psu), conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$), alkalinity (CaCO_3).

^aAverage of six samples.

D. Acclimation of seed sludge

The HUASB reactor was initially filled with 4 liters of the Anaerobic Digested sludge collected from Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narendrapur, near Kolkata. Batch treatment process was started with a highly biodegradable synthetic wastewater, which was fed in gradually decreasing amount and the raw slaughterhouse wastewater was added to it in gradually increasing amount in a certain total volume of feed. At the bottom of the reactor one litre feed was provided and the reactor was undergone for three days batch retention time. At the initial stage of the acclimation, the seed sludge was not able to degrade complex raw slaughterhouse wastewater and therefore a synthetic wastewater sample containing easily biodegradable substrate like

dextrose was mixed with the raw wastewater. The composition of synthetic wastewater is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Composition of synthetic wastewater

Sl. No.	Chemicals used	Amount (g/L)
1.	Dextrose anhydrous ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$)	10.0
2.	Ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3)	2.85
3.	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4)	0.45
4.	Ferric chloride (FeCl_3)	0.25
5.	Magnesium sulphate (MgSO_4)	22.5
6.	Calcium chloride (CaCl_2)	27.5
7.	Phosphate buffer ($\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4, \text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4$)	30.25

E. Batch study using slaughter house wastewater

At the first stage of batch operation, the reactor was added with 1000 ml total volume of feed for 10 cycles each continuing for 3 days. Hence, the amount of raw wastewater was increasing @ 5% of total volume. i.e. 50 ml/cycle. After attaining 10th cycle, it was observed that the reactor could handle 500 ml raw wastewater feed. Therefore, the volume raw wastewater feed was started to increase at 100 ml per cycle. This process was continued up to next 5 cycles at the second stage to make a total volume of raw wastewater to 1000 ml. After attaining 500 ml of raw wastewater, its amount was increased by 100 ml per cycle. In each trail, the batch monitoring was repeated three times to attain reproducible state showing constant COD removal efficiency over a certain batch retention time.

III. Results and discussion

A. Batch performance study

During batch operation of HUASB reactor, initial and final pH, COD, MLSS and MLVSS were regularly monitored. The detailed results of the batch study are presented in Table 4.

B. pH profile

Consistent pH level of 7.2–7.4 was observed in the effluent and in the consistent pH level of 7.01–

Table 4. Results of batch acclimation study with raw slaughterhouse wastewater

Acclimation Run No.	Vol. raw W.W. (ml)	Vol. syn. WW (ml)	Initial pH	Final pH	Initial COD (mg/L)	Final COD (mg/L)	COD Removal efficiency (%)
1.	50	950	7.48	6.86	1730	950	45
2.	100	900	7.47	6.84	2050	1060	48
3.	150	850	7.43	6.71	2470	1130	54
4.	200	800	7.48	6.77	2880	1310	54
5.	250	750	7.41	6.79	3010	1240	58
6.	300	700	7.36	6.84	3340	1269	62
7.	350	650	7.38	6.92	3580	1253	65
8.	400	600	7.39	7.01	3728	1156	69
9.	450	550	7.35	7.11	3920	1137	71
10.	500	500	7.32	7.19	4240	1102	74

7.09 was maintained in the inflow of the reactor. It indicates the favorable environment for biological conversion in the HUASB reactor. The increase in pH was possibly due to conversion of stronger VFA to weaker acids. pH profile with respect to various batch runs during the study are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. pH profile of the batch HUASB reactor.

C. COD removal efficiency

The reactor was maintained for a period of 90 days under different initial COD inputs. The COD removal efficiency was varied between 45% and 74%. During the stepped increase of COD concentration, the removal efficiency was gradually increased. The

profile of initial as well as final COD concentration and COD removal efficiency with respect to the batch runs during the study are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. COD removal efficiencies with respect to batch run.

The results of the batch study as shown in Table 4 revealed that the rate of increase in COD removal efficiency was slow, but uniform over various batch runs. At the same time, the COD removal efficiency did not reach to a satisfactory maximum value over the batch periods. Perhaps, it was due to the fact that the reactor was fed with the high COD concentration

in each batch run. However, the COD removal efficiency tends to increase with a faster rate after 5th batch run. It can be inferred that the HUASB reactor was getting more and more adaptability with real wastewater on account of reciprocal addition of synthetic and real wastewater. As a whole, the COD removal efficiency was gradually increased from 45% to 74% only due to the acclimation of the sludge with the raw slaughterhouse wastewater.

According to the Show *et al.*²⁶, the granules settling velocity is classified as three categories as low medium and high with respect to the below 20 m/h, between 20–50 m/h, above 50 m/h. In this study, the initial seed sludge has the settling velocity of 35 m/h, which gradually increased during entire batch operation. Under well grown stage it exhibited the high settling velocity of 58.9 m/h, which depicted the maximum granules maturation and stability of the reactor operation. At the initial stage, the biomass concentration of the reactor was 22,000 mg/L, which was enhanced to 36,000 mg/L at the end of the batch. The size of the sludge granule at the initial stage was 1–2 mm, which was increasing rapidly. At the end of the batch operation, the size of matured granules was observed to be between 3–4 mm on an average. However, the maximum granule size of 5–6 mm granules was also identified in few cases. It clearly demonstrates that the anaerobic process is a multistage process and various bacteria consortiums are responsible for it inside the reactor. In this study, 16s-rDNA test was performed to find the predominant bacteria present in the reactor. Consequently, *Christensenella timonensis*, was identified as the predominant species, which is said to be responsible for degradation of proteins and amino acids.

IV. Conclusion

The characterization of raw slaughterhouse wastewater revealed that it contained a high COD and BOD, which resembled with a high strength wastewater. The BOD of raw wastewater constituted about

90% of COD, which depicted its high biodegradability also. However, the nitrogen and phosphorous content in the raw wastewater was significantly low demanding for external supplement of the same. On the basis of batch study, it can be inferred that the anaerobic seed sludge was well accumulated, and it was capable to treat the raw slaughterhouse wastewater. In case of initial COD of 4240 mg/L under batch period of 72 h, final COD was observed to be 1102 mg/L showing 74% COD removal efficiency. From the 16s-rDNA study it was conformed that predominant bacteria present in the reactor was *Christensenella timonensis*. Due to the good MLSS growth and granule maturation the maximum settling velocity of the sludge was achieved as 58.9 m/h, which showed favorable environment for anaerobic treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater.

References

1. Z.Šereš, N. Maravić, A. Takači, I. Nikolić, D. Šoronja-Simović, A. Jokić and C. Hodur, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2016, **112**, 3132.
2. J. Shayegan, F. Ghavipankeh and P. Mirjafari, *Process Biochemistry*, 2005, **40(7)**, 2305.
3. G. S. Simate, J. Cluett, S. E. Iyuke, E. T. Musapatika, S. Ndlovu, L. F. Walubita, A. E. Alvarez, *Desalination*, 2011, **273(2)**, 235.
4. K. Sopajaree and A. Sancom, *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*, 2001, 49.
5. O. Tünay, I. Kabdasli, D. Orhon and E. Ates, *Water Science and Technology*, 1995, **32(12)**, 1.
6. J. B. Van Lier, A. Vashi, J. Van Der Lubbe, B. Heffernan and H. Fang, "Anaerobic sewage treatment using UASB reactors : Engineering and operational aspects", *Environmental anaerobic technology; applications and new developments*, World Scientific, Imperial College Press, London, 2010, 59-89.
7. E. I. Atuanya and M. Aigbirior, *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 2002, **77(2)**, 139.
8. C. F. Bustillo-Lecompte and M. Mehrvar, *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2015, **161**, 287.
9. C. F. Bustillo-Lecompte and M. Mehrvar, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2017, **141**, 278.
10. P. Jensen, T. Sullivan, C. Carney and D. Batstone, *Applied Energy*, 2014, **136**, 23.
11. L. Miranda, J. Henriques and L. Monteggia, *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 2005, **22(4)**, 601.

12. R. Rajagopal, D. I. Massé and G. Singh, *Bioresource Technology*, 2013, **143**, 632.
13. R. Rajakumar and T. Meenambal, *International Journal of Environmental Research*, 2008, **2(4)**, 401.
14. R. Rajakumar, T. Meenambal, J. R. Banu and I. Yeom, *International Journal of Environmental Science & Technology*, 2011, **8(1)**, 149.
15. I. Ruiz, M. C. Veiga, P. De Santiago and R. Blazquez, *Bioresource Technology*, 1997, **60(3)**, 251.
16. G. S. Mittal, *Bioresource Technology*, 2006, **97(9)**, 1119.
17. M. Monou, N. Pafitis, N. Kythreotou, S. R. Smith, D. Mantzavinos and D. Kassinos, *Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology*, 2008, **83(12)**, 1658.
18. O. Monroy, G. Famá, M. Meraz, L. Montoya and H. Macarie, *Water Research*, 2000, **34(6)**, 1803.
19. G. Najafpour, A. Zinatizadeh, A. Mohamed, M. H. Isa and H. Nasrollahzadeh, *Process Biochemistry*, 2006, **41(2)**, 370.
20. C. N. Nweke, J. T. Nwabanne and P. K. Igbokwe, *Open Journal of Renewable Energy and Sustainable Development*, 2014, **1**, 71.
21. Y. A. Oktem, O. Ince, P. Sallis, T. Donnelly and B. K. Ince, *Bioresource Technology*, 2008, **99(5)**, 1089.
22. E. Salminen and J. Rintala, *Bioresource Technology*, 2002, **83(1)**, 13.
23. A. Torkian, A. Eqbali and S. Hashemian, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 2003, **40(1)**, 1.
24. I. Öztürk, V. Eroglu, G. Ubay and I. Demir, *Water Science and Technology*, 1993, **28(2)**, 77.
25. J. Rajesh Banu and S. Kaliappan, *Journal of Environmental Engineering and Science*, 2007, **6(4)**, 415.
26. K.-Y. Show, Y. Wang, S.-F. Foong and J.-H. Tay, *Water Research*, 2004, **38(9)**, 2293.